

ISic3330

I.Sicily inscription 3330

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

building

Material

limestone

Object

architrave

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,system,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

2008.09.30

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Halaesa

Place of origin (modern)

near Castel di Tusa

Provenance

Found during excavations by Caretoni, summer 1956 in two separate locations to the east of the agora/'muro a bugnato'

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Halaesa, Area archeologica Halaesa Arconidea

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Letter Forms

Text

Apparatus

IEPΩ, Facella 2006: 178 n.127

Translation

Commentary

It is not possible to expand the text of block A: Facella (2006: 178 n.127) suggests that an iota can be read before the epsilon, but this is only the line of breakage on the stone, and his suggestion to read the name Hieron (i.e. King Hieron II of Syracuse, c.269-215 BC), if the monumentalisation of the agora belongs in the second century BC, is unlikely (if tempting). Campagna (2007: 117-118; followed by Prestianni Giallombardo 2012: 190 n.35) plausibly suggests that B should be restored to read [--έ]κ τῶν χ[ρημάτων--] ('from the funds...'), i.e. a reference to the financing of the building operation. In other words, the blocks may reasonably be imagined to form part of the dedicatory inscription of whatever structure was supported by the monumental 'muro a bugnato' which borders the west side of the principal street (the 'cardo massimo') as it runs north of the agora (and perhaps marks the eastern limit of the area of the so-called 'agora inferiore'), since the blocks were found in proximity to this wall. The letter forms are consistent with (but do not require) a date in the second century BC.

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undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-

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Block A: Photo J. Prag, courtesy Parco archeologico di Tindari